

The Effect of Teachers' Wellness Practices on the Teaching Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers in the Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon: Basis for the Development of a Self-Care Management Model

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teacher wellness, emotional wellness, psychological wellness, physical wellness, social wellness, spiritual wellness, teaching performance, public elementary school teachers, self-care management, teacher well-being, educational performance, descriptive-correlational research, Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon, Philippines education

Abstract. This study examined the wellness practices of public elementary school teachers in the Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon, and their effects on teaching performance. Specifically, it examined teachers' wellness practices in terms of emotional, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual aspects, their level of teaching performance, and the effect of wellness practices on teaching performance. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, and a self-developed survey questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents. Statistical tools such as frequency, mean, and multiple linear regression were utilized to analyze the data. The findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a high level of wellness practices, particularly in emotional and psychological aspects. Similarly, teachers showed a high level of teaching performance, especially in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and Learning Environment domains. However, results of the regression analysis showed that teachers' wellness practices do not have a significant effect on teaching performance, as indicated by a very low coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.018$). Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Based on the findings, it is concluded that while teachers actively engage in wellness practices and demonstrate strong teaching performance, wellness practices alone are not significant predictors of teaching performance. It is recommended that future interventions consider other contributing factors such as institutional support, workload management, and professional development opportunities to further enhance teacher performance.

Introduction

Teaching is widely acknowledged as a complex and demanding profession that requires a high level of intellectual, emotional, and social competence. Public elementary school teachers, in particular, are expected to address diverse learner needs, manage classroom dynamics, and fulfill multiple instructional and administrative responsibilities. These professional demands often expose teachers to varying levels of stress, which may significantly influence both their personal well-being and teaching performance.

Teacher stress is a growing concern due to its impact on teaching effectiveness, well-being, and job satisfaction (Kyriacou, C., 2001; Skaalvik, Einar M. & Skaalvik, Sidsel, 2017). It refers to the physical and psychological response to demands that exceed coping abilities (Lazarus, Richard S. & Folkman, Susan, 1984). Prolonged stress can cause burnout, emotional exhaustion, and reduced motivation (Maslach, Christina & Jackson, Susan E., 1981; Sokal, Lisa et al., 2020), ultimately affecting instruction quality and student outcomes.

In response to these challenges, teacher wellness has become a key factor in supporting both personal well-being and professional performance. Wellness is a multidimensional construct that includes emotional, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual health (Hettler, Bill, 1980; Myers, Jane E., Sweeney, Thomas J., & Witmer, J. Melvin, 2000). It goes beyond the absence of illness and is understood as an ongoing process of self-awareness and intentional actions aimed at improving quality of life and optimal functioning (Travis, John W. & Ryan, Regina S., 2004). Teachers who engage in wellness practices tend to show greater resilience, better mental health, and higher work engagement, all of which support effective teaching and long-term career satisfaction (Jennings, Patricia A. & Greenberg, Mark T., 2009).

Furthermore, wellness emphasizes the interconnectedness of the mind, body, and spirit. Emotional wellness enables teachers to manage stress effectively, while physical wellness supports energy and productivity. Social wellness fosters meaningful relationships within the school community, and spiritual wellness provides a sense of purpose and inner stability. These interconnected dimensions contribute to a teacher's ability to perform effectively and adapt to the evolving demands of the educational environment.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has emphasized the importance of teachers' mental health and well-being in sustaining effective teaching practices, particularly during challenging periods such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This commitment is reflected in policies such as DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016, which promotes research on teacher quality and well-being, and DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019, which supports capacity-building initiatives for teachers under the K to 12 program. More recently, DepEd has strengthened its efforts through the implementation of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services, which aims to address the holistic wellness of educators by providing psychological support and promoting resilience. These initiatives highlight the agency's recognition of the critical role of teacher well-being in ensuring quality education and improved learning outcomes.

Educational institutions and policymakers have increasingly recognized the importance of promoting teacher wellness through structured programs and support systems. Initiatives that focus on emotional regulation, physical self-care, social support, and reflective practices have been found to enhance teachers' well-being and work engagement (Dreer, 2021; Herman et al., 2020). These efforts highlight that teacher wellness is not only a personal concern but also an institutional priority that directly influences educational quality.

Despite the growing emphasis on wellness in the teaching profession and the presence of institutional support mechanisms, there remains a need to examine how specific wellness practices contribute to the teaching performance of public elementary school teachers. Understanding this relationship is essential for developing evidence-based interventions and structured wellness programs that support both teacher well-being and instructional effectiveness.

Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of wellness practices on the teaching performance of public elementary school teachers and to develop a wellness model based on the findings of the study.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the wellness practices of public elementary school teachers and their relationship to teaching performance. The descriptive aspect focused on identifying teachers' wellness practices in terms of emotional, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual dimensions, as well as their level of teaching performance. The correlational and predictive components determined whether wellness practices significantly influenced teaching performance through multiple linear regression analysis.

The research was conducted in the Sariaya West District, Division of Quezon, which consists of 23 public elementary schools. The locale was selected because it represents a typical Philippine public school setting where teachers experience diverse workloads and professional demands. A total of 195 teachers out of 394 were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation from all schools in the district.

A self-constructed survey questionnaire served as the main research instrument. Part I gathered the demographic and professional profile of the respondents, while Part II measured teachers' wellness practices across five dimensions using a 5-point Likert scale. Face and content validation of the instrument were conducted by educational experts. Teaching performance data were obtained through the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings.

Data gathering involved securing permission from school authorities, distributing the questionnaires, retrieving completed responses, and collecting IPCRF ratings. All gathered data were treated confidentially and used solely for research purposes.

For data analysis, descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to determine the level of wellness practices and teaching performance. Multiple linear regression analysis was utilized to determine whether teachers' wellness practices significantly predicted teaching performance, using the p-value and coefficient of determination (R^2) as bases for interpretation.

Results and Discussion

The findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a high level of wellness practices across emotional, psychological, physical, social, and spiritual dimensions. Emotional, psychological, and social wellness were consistently practiced, while physical and spiritual wellness were frequently practiced. These results indicate that teachers actively engage in practices that support their overall well-being despite the demands of the teaching profession.

In terms of teaching performance, teachers generally obtained a very satisfactory level of performance. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting were rated outstanding, while Learning Environment, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development were rated very satisfactory. The findings suggest that teachers consistently demonstrate competence, professionalism, and effectiveness in fulfilling their instructional responsibilities.

Regression analysis revealed that teachers' wellness practices did not significantly influence teaching performance. Although teachers demonstrated strong wellness practices and high teaching performance, the results showed that wellness practices alone were not significant predictors of performance. This implies that other factors, such as institutional support, workload management, leadership, and professional development opportunities may have a greater influence on teacher effectiveness.

Based on the findings, a Teacher Self-Care Management Model was developed to strengthen teachers' holistic well-being, particularly in the physical and spiritual dimensions, through intentional and structured self-care strategies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that public elementary school teachers in the Sariaya West District consistently practice wellness behaviors across emotional, psychological, social, physical, and spiritual dimensions, with emotional and psychological wellness being the most evident. Teachers also demonstrated a high level of teaching performance, reflecting competence and professionalism in carrying out their instructional responsibilities. However, the findings revealed that wellness practices do not significantly influence teaching performance, indicating that teacher effectiveness may be shaped more by organizational and professional factors such as workload, school climate, leadership support, and access to resources and professional development opportunities.

The findings imply that while wellness practices may not directly predict teaching performance, they remain essential in sustaining teachers' overall well-being, resilience, motivation, and professional longevity. Thus, schools and educational institutions should continue promoting holistic wellness programs that support teachers' physical, emotional, social, psychological, and spiritual health. The proposed Teacher Self-Care Management Model may serve as a framework for strengthening teacher well-being through structured and sustainable self-care strategies. Furthermore, future studies may explore other variables that could better explain variations in teaching performance and further validate the applicability of the proposed model in different educational contexts.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that there are no known competing financial or personal relationships that could have influenced the findings, interpretation, or presentation of this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in this study were obtained from survey responses and researcher observation conducted for academic purposes. The datasets are not publicly available due to ethical considerations and institutional restrictions, but may be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request, subject to approval.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.

